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INVESTIGATING GENDER PERCEPTIONS ON TECHNOLOGY USE IN PAKISTANI ELT CLASSROOMS: A SURVEY-BASED STUDY

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Abstract

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Students' motivation is increased when they use the internet. The importance of information and communication technology in course books has evolved in all educational fields to move towards modern methods of teaching. This research was based on inspecting the perception of males and females concerning the use of technology in English language teaching classrooms by utilizing quantitative research procedures. The perception of gender towards the utilization of technology in ELT classrooms was explored through a questionnaire. The survey was administered on the accessibility and readiness of the contributors. The sample size (N=90) comprises English Language students from various classes at the University of Okara (Department of English Language). The results of the study revealed that females have greater knowledge of English language learning and technological integration in ELT due to variations in these values and also females have a larger tendency to favour the use of technology in ELT classes than males. The findings elucidated that technology has profoundly shaped our societal fabric, exerting distinct permutations upon our collective ethos and cognitive paradigms. By taking into account any potential gender-based prejudices or barriers, educators may create a more thorough and beneficial learning environment that motivates all students to actively engage with technology.

Keywords: Technology, Integration, Gender, Societal Impact, Teaching Strategies, English Language Learning

Introduction

In English as a second language (ESL), the study of gender has been utilized as a foundation, and it has discovered virtually exposition to replicate womanly dominance in language learning. Gender differences in ESL classroom teaching have been discovered in studies. Some academics query whether gender is even a worthwhile theme to study and whether women have higher language skills. This research paper investigates the part of gender in learning. It is assumed that women do not outperform males in second language, or second language, skills. (McCaughan, 2009). Van Dijk (1998) supposes that "if there is one vast field of critical research on discourse and language that thus far was not carried out within a CDA perspective, it is that of gender". "Gender equality has been examined not only in the ELT domain but also in other powerful media including print media and mass media" (Chanzanagh & Haghpor, 2010; Danova, 2006; del-Teso-Craviotto, 2006; Goffman, 1976; Isanovic, 2006; Ohara & Saft, 2003). Furthermore, incorporating cutting-edge technology, in particular, into ELT pedagogy, is expected to result in significant changes (Iqbal & Rafi, 2018). In the 21st century, vigorous English ideologies and presumed tensions imitate one of the difficulties of ELT. The designation of "English" for example, institute theme is being called into question, as it may be motivated by theoretical civilizations and the essential for dispositive in place of a move to a cross-functional topic of the statement (Larsen-Freeman & Freeman, 2008; Leung & Valdes, 2019). Teachers must constantly theorize and paradigm practice, information, and opinions to give nearby pertinent ELT as a result of the evolution of the topic criticism and the variety of instructional contexts. (Kumaravadelu, 2001, 2006). It is frequently postulated that technology in language learning will make learners more vigorous and well-organized, will upgrade learning and teaching, will contribute to actual and winsome learning outcomes, and will one step ahead

produce learners for the personnel (Brown & Cuban, 2001). The importance of information and communication technology in course books has evolved in all educational fields to move towards modern methods of teaching. (Hismanoğlu, 2011).

Purpose Statement

Pakistan is a developing country that recognizes the value of technology in the educational system. This research will analyze what males and females perceive about this integration. The perception of students toward technology based on gender in Pakistan, as well as how students perceived the use of technology in the classroom based on gender, and the reasons for this.

Research Objectives

1. To explore the perception of males and females regarding the practice of technology in English Language Teaching classrooms
2. To explore which class of gender mostly prefer by using technology in ELT classrooms

Questions of Research

1. What is the perception of males and females about practicing technology in English Language Teaching classrooms?
2. Which class of gender mostly prefers using technology in ELT classrooms?

Significance of the Study

The study is significant since it will provide new ideas and methods of thinking for philosophers as well as a way for students to obtain assistance and experts to develop. More study in the realm of technology in ELT is required. On the advantages of using technology in language acquisition generally, the results of the current study are anticipated to be clear. The study's findings may be useful to a variety of people. Additionally, this research may benefit educators by simplifying their roles, as well as students by assisting them in easily and smoothly absorbing the English language with technology. Last but not least, this work can motivate more research on the same subject by other scholars, which

would enhance both domestic and foreign literature.

Literature Review

2.1. English Language Teaching (ELT)

The figure of surveys into the research inclinations of a scientific area has increased in recent decades. Relevant studies, for example, in the fields of English language teaching and learning and applied linguistics, (Hsu, 2005; Ker, Adams & Skyrme, 2013; Lazaraton, 2000; Liu & Zhang, 2015; Richards, 2009; Yihong, Lichun & Jun 2001) have scattered knowledge around research application. For example, Lazaraton (2000) identifies one of the challenging matters that applied linguistics experts seem to deficiency in terms of their aptitude to conduct experiential research. Lazaraton also contends that figures should be used in conjunction with the fundamental features, and disdain her normal use of ANOVA, the researcher expresses concern about the accuracy of statistical procedures. Lazaraton (2005) examined published articles over eleven years in her subsequent study. The majority of the research (86%) in the four papers under review used measurable methodology.

Anyone who has lived through the last decade of scientific progression comprehends how quickly our world is altering. And what occurs external of our education settings, in the actual world, will inevitably influence "what we do inside our classrooms, lecture halls, schools, and colleges". In each case, we consider how these new developments will affect English language teachers and students in the future". (Hockly et al., 2018).

The significance of materials in language teaching or learning has long been recognized (McGrath, 2013). "Most language courses rely heavily on teaching materials. Language teaching today would be impossible to achieve without the extensive use of commercial materials" (Richards, 2001). This study indicates substantial design and the usage of reliable materials in the English as a foreign language classroom, as well as the importance

of these materials for linguistic students. They supplement outdated instructions and can be engaging for students. (Ahmed, 2017). One achievable educational implementation is to intermix English songs into ELT. This study contributes conceptual dissension and practical assistance to utilize English songs in ELT. (Shen, 2003).

2.2. Uses of Technology in English Language Learning

The ignored ICT devices should never be included in the lessons (Murat Hismanoğlu, 2011). This study justified the use and development of ICT, as well as its impact on ELT over the last three years. According to this development, it not only affected classrooms but also encouraged teachers to teach languages. The taxonomies of CALL's implementation by Stephen Bax and Mark Warschauer are used for this purpose. They also followed the teaching and language learning development methods from the beginning to the end of CALL (1980 to 1990) from CALL to WEB 2.0. Finally, they examined a summary of the future implications of technology for ELT learning. (Gavin Dudeney & Nicky Hockly, 2012). Information and Communication Technology (ICT) developed rampant throughout the past three decennia, noticeably switching various directions in commercial and barter regions. This study examines modern ideas, applications, and practical information regarding the nature of hybrid learning mainly and Computer Assisted Language Learning (CALL) a style of hybrid learning explicitly used in English Language Teaching (ELT), specifically. Each of these will expectantly upgrade awareness to enforce hybrid learning in ELT to strengthen our learner attainment. (Pardede, 2012). The one basic reason for this social uprightness of students is not badly influenced by the similar scope when English as an international language viewpoint is the main element of ELT. (Phillipson, 2001).

Embellishment has made education a foreign language essential in the twenty-first century. English comes first because it is the

language of most professional and scientific expansion, providence, management, and favored amusement (Graddol, 2006). Instructing English has been around for a prolonged time, and its importance is growing. As (Graddol, 1997) predicted in his research two thousand, there will be a billion English language learners and this count reaches double value or magnitude a decade later. ELT has all the time been linked to mechanization (Shinghal, 1997). Learners often found the procedure to be monotonous and uninteresting (Nawaila et al., 2020).

2.3. Integrating technology in ELT classroom

When pupils study through technology, it supports them to create advanced level rational skills. Finally, it is critical to draw learners' attention to the English language, the accurate mixture of multimedia & teaching procedures (Arifah, 2014). Two diverse views on what method to integrate technology in the classroom were described. "First, the cognitive approach allows students to maximize their language exposure while also developing their knowledge in a meaningful setting" These technologies include manuscript renovation software systems and multimedia imitation software. Students must be able to exercise actual services through sincere social connections in this context. This can be accomplished over reliable projects completed in association with pupils. (Warschauer, 2000). Scholars from various past years have corroborated the positive influence of the utilization of information and communication technology in teaching. An exploration of similar studies with the sole objective of computing the recent study swing on the endowment of ingenious technology concerning English language learning and instructing. For this research 50 published articles from 2000- 2018 were used. These articles were taken from EBSCO and Science Direct. SPSS was used as a data analysis tool. (Nawaila, 2020).

As educational institutions' technology groundwork increases, one ordinary source of

study is the underuse of laptops and other technological means in the classroom. Instructors and teachers are mostly criticized for the imperfection of intermingling technological tools during their teaching. These problems with classroom technological utilization or the advancing way of instructors' technological intermixing are elaborated in conditions of executive evolution inference. (Hixon & Buckenmeyer, 2009). This research sum-up with contemplation of the recent situation of the sphere also the prospective for technology in assistance to integrate technology in learning learning-centered environment. (Pellegrino & Quellmalz, 2014). This study elaborates on the use of technological tools, social media, and print media during the learning of the English language and teaching of the English language at the level of undergraduate. This research reveals that eager response has become the reason for motivation for learning a language. It is concluded that this research plays an important role in making planned language learning and teaching investigations from unplanned, it also produced a syllabus-oriented package. (Rao, 2014).

The efficiency of virtual classrooms is examined from the viewpoints of 35 online language learning (OLL) teachers in this study. Teachers can engage with students more personally and give them feedback that is more tailored to their needs. Students' language skills may advance more quickly and effectively as a result of this. In conclusion, this study analyzed that the participants in this research were very positive about the efficiency of online classrooms for OLL. They believe that online classrooms propose a variety of benefits over physical classrooms and these online classrooms proved to be beneficial tools for learning language (Manegre & Sabiri, 2022; Sabiri & Shah, 2023). Technology has been a big source of advancement in recent eras it has changed our societal lifestyle and our assumptions in the developing world. This is the need of the hour every learner and individual

must be aware of the usage of technology and technology-based programming. (Ibrahim, 2010).

Gender in Educational Context:

According to Ekstrand (1980), there are few studies on gender alterations in Language 2 learning, and there is no information on gender and overseas language attainment. Nonetheless, Ekstrand opposes himself later by claiming "consistent superiority of girls in all variables". Ekstrand concludes that similar research "does not support any safe conclusions about gender differences in L2 learning (Ekstrand, 1980).

According to Baumeister (1988), sex difference studies might not be a prolific study topic because gender variations can be used to justify female discernment and subjugation. He theorizes that, given the feminist opinion that discrimination saturates civilization, sex differences research should be discontinued or, at the very least, limited. Furthermore, research into language and gender can lead to pedagogy that benefits both genders" (Baumeister, 1988).

The discoveries are encouraging to throw back a balanced presentation of men and women this research also provides a ray of expectation for the next generation in ELT textbooks. (Studies et al., 2017). In the last three decades, suffragists and professors have studied the multiplex interactivity of gender with multiple matters for example authority, political authority, occupation, and identification (Visser, 2002). Cameron (1995) states, "A crude historical-typological account of feminist linguistic approaches since 1973 would probably distinguish between three models of language and gender, the deficit model, the cultural difference model, and the dominance model. This interpretation accorded well with one of the assumptions made by early gender scholars such as Lakoff (1975), who saw women's language as the "language of powerlessness," a reflection of their subordinate place about men. Block (2002) states that the view of gender is

essentialized in that it is about having certain characteristics, which are determined by the environment, and which are stable throughout one's lifetime.

Furthermore, in the Dominance model, women are perceived to perform their 'woman-ness' in an ethnomethodological frame as they continually negotiate their position of relative powerlessness vis a vis man (Cameron, 1995). Education plays a role as the requisite instrument in bringing off gender sovereignty and approval of females or males inscribe gender interstice in dissemination chance and expedient. Gender distinctions are surprisingly, an elemental certainty of sociolinguistic existence and it is not astonishing that are contemplated in language learning. Furthermore, there are definite aspects of language learning which are pertinent for males and other aspects may be utilized by females. In other studies, these discriminations rely not just on the addresser of gender but on the sex of the addressee (Ansary and Babaii, 2003).

2.5. Research Gap

Technology integration in the English language Classroom teaching is an important and pressing issue in today's world. To avoid lawlessness and inconvenience when using technology in ELT, all advanced countries have developed new policies. Pakistan is a developing country that recognizes the value of technology in the educational system. Work on ELT continues in Pakistan. This research contributes to the consideration of gender standpoints on the incorporation of technology in (ELT). The current study aimed to explore the perception of males and females regarding the practice of technology in English Language Teaching classrooms and to explore which class of gender mostly prefers using technology in ELT classrooms. The study tried to fill the gap in the literature regarding the use of technology in education concerning males and females and tried to contribute to this field by recruiting a sample from a public university in Okara. This researcher tried to understand the

usage of technology concerning genders and the reason for difference if any was found among the preferences of the genders.

Methodology

Theoretical Framework

The theory of "technological determinism" forged by [Thorstein Veblen in the 1920s](#) (1857-1929) was adopted for this research as it circles the postulation that in every designated society technology characterizes its description. Technology is perceived as the driving force of traditions in a community and regulates its history. In this research second hypothesis proposed by Langdon Winner for this theory was explored which states "Changes in technology are the primary and most important source that leads to change in the society" (Adler et al., n.d.). This research examines whether it is true in Pakistani settings and what gender will perceive about this hypothesis now.

Figure 1. Theoretical framework

The theory of technological determinism is a theory of degeneracy. The objective of this theory is to produce a causative connection between society's nature and technology. It struggles to elaborate what and to whom have administering authority in human phenomenon. This theory examines the magnitude to which the thoughts and actions of human beings are regulated by technological factors. Karl Marx accepted that technological advancement led the way for construction in a community and it eventually affected the political, economic, and cultural factors of the community. He illustrated this point by describing how with the origination of the steam mill a primitive society that relied upon

hand mills gradually evolved into a manufacturer-investor society.

Two propositions were supposed by Langdon Winner for this theory

1. The technology of a specified society is a foundational inspirer of different ways through which a society subsists.
2. Variations in technology are the central and most salient source that led to substitutes in society.

Figure 2. Technology in environment

Data collection tools population and sample size

This research is quantitative research regulated by utilizing quantitative research methods. In quantitative research, numerical data are gathered and analyzed to characterize, explain, forecast, or control relevant occurrences ([Mills & Gay, 2019](#)). The sample size N=90 comprised English Language students from various classes at the University of Okara's Department of English Language in the province of Punjab Pakistan. The perception of gender towards the utilization of technology in ELT classrooms was explored through a questionnaire which initiated with certain information and then divided into two segments. The first section implores personal information about participants in which name, gender, age, qualification, and semester are explored. The second section uses the questionnaire "Gender perception towards technology in ELT" which is further divided into four segments (content knowledge, technological knowledge, integration of technology in ELT learning, and student perception of the use of technology to improve

their language skills). The second section of the questionnaire comprises 35 items that are ranked utilizing a Likert-type scale from 1-5 in which 1 constitutes 'strongly disagree' and 5 constitute 'strongly agree'. An example of questions is:

1. You think technology saves time and energy
2. Do you agree that technology spreads knowledge and information very fast
3. Are you happy or satisfied while using technology in ELT classrooms
4. Technological devices make us addicted to technology

The data gathered throughout the survey questionnaire was examined using quantitative research methods e.g., descriptive statistics t-test and ANOVA the outcomes were accessible by using tables, charts, and graphs. The questionnaire was adapted from (Education, 2018; Technologies, n.d.; Ammade et al., 2018; Akah et al., 2022; Katemba, 2019; Studies, 2018a; Studies, 2018b).

Results and Discussion

4.1.1. Demographic Information

The graph shows the gender distribution of the 45 participants from each gender, who made up an equal number of male and female students in the research study.

Figure 3. Gender representation

The distribution of participant ages in the research study is shown on the graph. Twenty-year-old or older participants make up roughly 10 to 11% of the whole group. The majority, between 47 and 52%, are between the ages of 21 and 24. Participants between the ages of 25 and 28 make up a sizeable majority, between 29 and 32%. People over the age of 28 make up

a smaller fraction of the population (5 percent of the total), which they make up.

Figure 4. Qualification of participants

Table 1. Cronbach's Alpha for questionnaire

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
.920	.926	31

To understand participant attitudes toward the use of technology in ELT, the researcher computed the mean and standard deviation of the responses provided by participants. The average response from female participants ranged from 3.73 to 4.62, indicating that they generally agreed with the questionnaire's questions about the use of technology in ELT. The higher mean score of 4.62 indicates that there was strong support for using technology in ELT among the female participants. The mean score for male responses, however, ranged from 3.6 to 4.44. The lower mean scores compared to the female responses indicate that male participants showed usually lesser agreement, even if this range also demonstrates a generally positive attitude toward technology in ELT. The researcher also observed that the standard deviation of female responses ranged from 0.49 to 1.31 and male responses ranged from 0.62 to 1.27. the data depicted that most of the participants agreed and appreciated the use of technology in ELT.

Table 2. Std, Mean of males and females

	N	Female		Male	
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Mean	Std. Deviation
I have sufficient knowledge of English language learning technologies.	45	4.4889	0.50553	4.2667	0.8634
I have various ways and strategies for developing my understanding of English.	45	4.4	0.61791	4.3556	0.60886
I know the technologies that I can use for learning English.	45	4.6	0.49543	4.4444	0.65905
I keep up with important new technologies for language learning.	45	4.3333	0.70711	4.1333	0.91949
I have had sufficient opportunities to work with different technologies in ELT classrooms.	45	4.5333	0.72614	3.8444	0.92823
I know about a lot of different technologies that can be implemented in ELT classrooms.	45	4.2889	0.78689	3.9556	1.06506
. Integration of technology stimulates students' motivation, concentration & learning.	45	4.6222	0.71633	3.9111	0.97286
I like the strategies that appropriately combine English, technologies, and teaching approaches.	45	4.4444	0.62361	4.1778	0.83364
I can encourage online interactivity among students and teachers while English Language Learning.	45	4.4	0.71985	4.1333	0.84208
Using technology in ELT class is very beneficial.	45	4.4889	0.62603	4.1111	0.93474
Technological devices make us addicted to technological machines	45	4.3333	0.60302	3.9778	0.83907
Old-fashioned ways (using pen and paper, course books, blackboards, etc.) are more useful than technology in classes.	45	3.9556	1.31349	3.6	1.05313
I appreciate the usage of technology in classes for English language learning.	45	4.6	0.49543	4.1556	0.9524
I think critically about the use of technology to enhance my language learning	45	4.2889	0.78689	4.0444	1.06506
Integration of technology facilitates the students in learning English	45	4.3556	0.80214	4.2667	0.8634
Lack of technological equipment affects students' language learning	45	4.2889	0.86923	4.0222	0.9412
I feel satisfied while using technology in the ELT classroom	45	4.4	0.71985	3.9333	0.93905
Teachers' and students' experience of technology is beneficial for ELT	45	4.5556	0.62361	4.0889	0.73306
I 4 that technology can spread knowledge and information very fast	45	4.4222	0.81153	4.1778	0.91176
Technological tools can be used as curriculum materials at Schools/Colleges	45	4.3111	0.70137	4.0667	0.91453
Technological tools can replace teachers in teaching English	45	4.2222	1.06363	3.8667	1.27208
I think technology use does not have noteworthy value for human societies in general	45	3.7333	1.30384	3.8444	1.16688
I think technology saves energy and time	45	4.5556	0.62361	4.3556	0.64511
I think the use of Zoom and WhatsApp can help the students eliminate hesitation/ lack of confidence in practicing English	45	4.4222	0.81153	3.9111	1.12457
I think the use of Zoom and WhatsApp is strategic for learning English, especially for discussion and question-answer	45	4.2667	0.93905	4.0222	1.03328
I think students must use technology in all subject matters	45	4.5556	0.72474	4.2444	0.98062
The use of technological tools makes learning more entertaining than traditional ways of teaching	45	4.4444	0.72474	4.1333	0.86865
The use of technological tools has improved my reading skills	45	4.3778	0.88649	4.4222	0.62118
The use of technological tools improves my listening skills	45	4.3333	0.79772	4.3111	0.73306
The use of technological tools improves my speaking skills	45	4.3556	0.88306	4.2444	0.88306
The use of technological tools improves my writing skills	45	4.1333	0.96766	4.2	0.94388

The graph shows the 4.104 participants, accounting for 48% of the total identified as males. In contrast, 4.371 participants, making up 52% of the total identified as females. These figures insights into the disparities in gender perspectives on the use of technology in ELT.

Figure 5. Comparison of means

The responses of females have a mean of 4.371, with 3.733 being the lowest value and 4.622 being the highest. The variance of .035 suggests that there is not much variation and that the results are characteristically near to the mean.

Table 3. Females mean comparison

	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Max / Min	Variance	N of Items
Item Mean	4.371	3.733	4.622	.889	1.238	.035	31
Item Variance	.636	.245	1.725	1.480	7.029	.124	31

Male responses range from a minimum of 3.600 to a maximum of 4.444, with an average value of 4.104. Due to the low variance of .037, it can be concluded that the scores for these items are impartially near to the mean.

Table 4. Males mean comparison

	Mean	Minimum	Maximum	Range	Max / Minimum	Variance	N of Items
Item Mean	4.104	3.600	4.444	.844	1.235	.037	31
Item Variance	.846	.371	1.618	1.247	4.365	.081	31

4.2. Discussion

Thorstein Veblen's (1857–1929) theory of "technological determinism," which revolves around the hypothesis that technology characterizes every defined society's description, was utilized for this study. Technology is seen as the factor that controls a community's history and drives its customs. In this study, the second Langdon Winner supposition for this theory—that "Changes in technology are the principal and most important cause that leads to change in the society"—was investigated. (Adler et al., n.d.). The only claim made by technological determinism is that technology and its applications have a substantial impact on how we survive. The proposal is prominently mentioned in popular interest and political discourse, such as the claim that the internet and social media have changed society and providence. This study investigates if it is accurate in the Pakistani context and how gender will perceive this claim going forward. The findings of this research elucidate that technology has profoundly shaped our societal fabric, exerting distinct permutations upon our collective ethos and cognitive paradigms.

4.2.1. Research Question 1

Because the researcher's primary goal was to acquire data regarding the integration of technology in ELT, the questionnaire was created taking technological knowledge and ELT integration into consideration (Technologies, n.d.; Studies, 2018; Education, 2018; Katemba, 2019). The overall Cronbach's Alpha reliability of the questionnaire used in this study was 920, which was deemed to be an ideal coefficient one, a high level of internal consistency, or a high degree of correlation between the scale items (Alshammari et al., 2017). The maximum mean from female responses was 4.6 and 4.4 from male responses of knowledge about the English language and technological integration in ELT. The variation in these values claims that

females have more knowledge about English language learning and technological integration in ELT. (Garcia-holgado et al., 2018; Phillipson, 2001)

To give learners enough opportunities to work with various technologies in ELT classrooms and to keep up with important new technologies for language learning, the second main theme, technological knowledge, was further divided into three subthemes. Many different technologies can be used in ELT classrooms. (Pardede, 2012; Aykut Arslan, 2008; Dudeney & Hockly, 2012). Male responses had a maximum mean value of 4.1 and female responses had a maximum mean value of 4.5. This variation in the mean values demonstrates that males have fewer opportunities to use various technologies in ELT courses and that they are less knowledgeable about such technology. Students benefit from tactics that effectively blend English technologies and instructional philosophies because they are motivated, focused, and learn more. (Iqbal & Rafi, 2018; Cuban, 2001; Murat Hismanoglu, 2011). In comparison to men, this value demonstrates that women are more focused and appreciate learning strategies that integrate technologies and instructional methods.

The students believe that integrating technology makes it easier for them to learn English, and they also believe that a lack of technical resources hinders their ability to do so. (Nawaila, 2020). Male and female mean values of 4.3 and 4.2, respectively, show that responses from both sexes are about comparable, with females placing greater emphasis than males. Females and males' mean values of 4.3 and 4.2, respectively, show that responses from both sexes are about comparable, with females placing greater emphasis than males. The usage of WhatsApp and Zoom is important for learning English, particularly for debate, and using technology to teach makes learning more enjoyable than traditional methods (Manegre & Sabiri, 2022;

Sabiri & Shah, 2023). The fourth and final theme of the questionnaire was focused on students' perceptions of how technology is used to help learners enhance their language skills in reading, writing, speaking, and listening. The female responses have a mean value of 4.3 and males have 4.4, so males support this statement more strongly as compared to females.

4.2.2. Research Question 2

According to the results of the statistical analysis of the questionnaire, it can be said that when compared to males, females have a stronger propensity to favor the use of technology in ELT classrooms. Examples and discussion are as follows. Technology has been useful in ELT, as students can promote online interaction between themselves and their teachers while studying the English language. (Hockly et al., 2018; Salehi & Salehi, 2011; Education, 2018). Regarding this statement on the Cronbach Alpha mean scale, the data showed that males scored an average of 4.1 while females displayed an average rating of 4.4. These numbers show that females were more likely to agree than males believe that technology has a lot of potential for (ELT). Additionally, these findings imply that integrating technology into ELT classes has the potential to promote a lively and passionate mode of interaction between teachers and students, improving the learning process as a whole.

The use of technology in ELT classrooms by teachers and students was a positive experience for both learners and teachers. (Hixon & Buckenmeyer, 2009 ; Pellegrino & Quellmalz, 2014). Technology integration in (ELT) classrooms has proven to be a collaborative situation for teachers and students. This claim is supported by the fact that, on a mean scale, male respondents gave an average rating of 4.0, while female respondents gave an average rating of 4.5. The obvious difference between these mean ratings indicates that, in comparison to the

male respondents, female respondents felt more content when using technology as a tool to facilitate language learning. In addition, women indicated a stronger belief in the effectiveness of technology in facilitating language learning.

Students benefit from tactics that effectively blend English technologies and instructional philosophies because they are motivated, focused, and learn more. (Cuban, 2001; Murat Hismanoglu, 2011). The examination of the data showed that whereas female participants showed a higher mean score of 4.6, male participants showed a mean score of 4.1. This disparity suggests that females have a higher propensity for focus and a higher appreciation for pedagogical strategies that combine technological innovations with instructional methodologies. In other words, females typically exhibit increased focus and a stronger aptitude for learning tactics that utilize pioneering technologies and instructional techniques.

Technology can convey information and knowledge very quickly; thus, students should use it in all subject areas. (Pellegrino & Quellmalz, 2014; Rao, 2014). Male participants produced a mean value of 4.2, while female participants showed a higher average of 4.5, showing a noticeable discrepancy between the two groups, according to the analysis of the data collected. This discrepancy implies that women have a strong propensity for using technology in a variety of areas. Females exhibit a thorough and progressive attitude to education by promoting the use of technology in all subject areas.

When compared to male corresponding items, females appear to have a larger propensity to support the incorporation of technology in the field of ELT, according to a thorough examination of aggregated mean scores and the aforementioned discussion. Moreover, the research results imply that women have a disposition that is more

receptive to incorporating technology innovations within the context of ELT. This increased support can be attributed to several things, including a deeper understanding of the transformative effects that digital tools have on pedagogical practices, a greater appreciation for the potential benefits of technology in language acquisition, and increased recognition of the effectiveness of technology-mediated learning environments. This disparity in opinions between the genders suggests that initiatives to adopt and yield from technology advancements in ELT may succeed better among the female population.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study indicates that females are more likely than males to favour the use of technology in ELT classes and have more knowledge of English language acquisition and technological integration in ELT. The results of TD's second hypothesis demonstrate how technology has significantly altered our collective ethos and cognitive frameworks, reshaping our social fabric. Teachers may design a more thorough and useful learning environment that encourages all students to actively engage with technology by accounting for any potential gender-based stereotypes or hurdles. Females have greater knowledge of English language learning and technological integration in ELT due to variations in these values. Technology has been beneficial in ELT since students can enhance online engagement between themselves and their teachers while learning English.

Furthermore, females have a larger tendency to favour the use of technology in ELT classes than males. The research findings showed that women are more open to bringing technological advancements within the setting of ELT. This increased support can be attributed to a variety of factors, including a better understanding of the transformative effects that digital tools have on pedagogical

practices, a greater appreciation for the potential benefits of technology in language acquisition, and a better understanding of the effectiveness of technology-mediated learning environments. This gender discrepancy in opinions suggests that programs to accept and benefit from technological improvements in ELT may fare better among females. Moreover, this study explicates probable gender differences in technological admittance in ELT classrooms. Instructors and representatives can work toward providing equivalent access to technology for every learner, irrespective of gender, by recognizing and considering these gaps.

5.4. Recommendations

- The learners should use technology for intelligent and productive purposes rather than wasting their valuable time on amusement and idleness.
- To encourage students to use technology in their learning, teachers should assign project work that is technologically based.
- Regardless of any obvious gender prejudices, students should be given plenty of opportunities for language learning together with the seamless integration of technology.
- Government organizations and educational policymakers should take steps to promote equal student technology adoption, disregarding any gender-based predispositions.

5.5. Limitations

The study's first drawback was that it only included ELT students. The opinions of the students were also perceived by several departments.

- The only method used to conduct the current study is quantitative research.
- Only questionnaires were employed in the study as a means of gathering data.
- Additionally, data can be gathered from semi-structured student interviews.

- Another drawback was that the study was limited to one university's English department; consequently, a further study could be carried out using a mixed strategy to include students from several universities to get better results.

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